

Efficient electron transport layer for high performance Polymer Light-Emitting Devices

Mora Veera Madhava Rao, Cheol-Hee Moon

Department of Display Engineering, Hoseo University, Asan, 336-795, Republic of Korea

Tel.: 82-41-540-5923, E-mail: madhavmora@yahoo.com

Organic and polymer emitting diodes(O/PLED) are promising display devices because of their preferential properties such as fast response, high brightness, low driving voltage, wide viewing angle, and light weight. When a voltage is applied to an OLED device, holes are injected from the anode and electrons are injected from the cathode, with both carriers moving toward the opposite electrode and recombining in the emissive layer, resulting in the production of light emission. However, the stability and performance of OLED are in needs of further improvements due to imbalanced hole and electron fluxes and poor charge injection efficiency. Therefore, considerable efforts have been devoted to the studies on interfacial engineering for improving the device performance [1-4].

We have fabricated highly efficient polymer light-emitting devices(PLED) from ionic compound dispersed water soluble non- conjugated molecular materials(PBD), which was used as hole blocking and electron transport layer(HB-ETL) on the top of commercially available light emitting polymer. The device with HB-ETL showed a maximum current efficiency of 2.6 cd/A, while the one without HB-ETL showed an efficiency of 1.4cd/A. They propose that the better performance in PLED with PBD layer was to a well-balanced charge injection in emitting layer after the enhanced electron transport due to ionic compound in the PBD layer.

Fig.1 Current Efficiency -Voltage characteristics of the device with and without HB-ETL layers

The Current efficiency versus voltage characteristics of these Polymer based devices with different cathode structures are shown in Fig.1. It can be seen that the current efficiency of PLEDs is also enhanced by introducing a thin layer is inserted between polymer layer and cathode

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